

The Advantage of Animated Advertisements in Today's Era

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Abstract:- There is no doubt that animation is quickly emerging as one of the most significant trends and approaches in advertising in the modern era. Animated commercials offer a video that is entertaining in addition to being promotional, so there is no need to wonder why that is the case. The Consumer will be unable to tear their eyes away from the sights and motion. Considering the significance of the purpose of this research is to provide a comparison and analysis of the most recent animated commercials. The study examines the differences and similarities between animated and traditional forms of advertising.

I. INTRODUCTION

There is no denying the fact that videos are a much more engaging and successful form of advertising than images. That is clear, given how readily films can capture viewers' attention and turn them into potential customers for the promoted offering, service, or product. As a result, video advertising has been increasingly popular recently. Statistics demonstrate that most individuals (86%) prefer to watch videos for businesses and items (McCormick, 2021).

On social media, 82% prefer watching a video to reading or checking a post. 64% of customers who see the video go on to purchase the products, services, or product advertisements. People process and enjoy visual material 60,000 times faster on average. Videos, particularly animated multimedia, are more engaging than text-based information. It takes less than a tenth of a second to capture viewers' attention (Hoque, 2020). It has long been recognized that animation has significantly impacted society. While advertising. Celebrities, advertising firms, production companies, animation studios, Businesses, and sectors have adopted animation to capture and represent companies, goods, and services while hooking the Consumer psychologically and logically (Thompson M. C., 2019). However, animated Real-world aspects in advertising are being replaced with cartoons, objects, and settings. The extraordinary dependence on animation in advertising has increased as technology has progressed. It has been increasing

(animate2explain, 2017). For instance, in the realm of digital, Videos and ads be practical marketing tools.

Today, the CEO and President of Darvideo Animation Studio, Yuriy Polyashko, Because the audience's tolerance for waiting is short; animation has become a popular kind of entertainment. Everyday encounters and a crucial marketing strategy that keeps the audience from dullness (Polyashko, 2019). He continues by saying that scientific advancements support the since "90% of the information is communicated to the brain," the concept of animated or visual material is entirely visual, establishing the legitimacy of and defending the use of animation in marketing devices. According to statistics supplied by Unbounce, animated infographics videos with motion graphics also boost conversion by 20%. Animoto estimates that 4 out of 5 consumers prefer animated infographics and motion graphic films.

Additionally, research from Wordstream has revealed that advertisers that use videos - incredibly animated and visual material, increase income by 49% more quickly and significantly. Those who do not rely on videos. For instance, an animated commercial may create Virtual worlds with fictitious people that are not necessarily required to be realistic; as a result, Storytelling appeals to the imagination of the audience (animate2explain, 2017). Additionally, while most individuals read pages and paragraphs, not everyone will see and comprehend an animated film. Forbes reports that 95% of users, when watching animated videos, just 10% of viewers can comprehend the material. The subject of the writings. Animated commercials have become a popular type. Consequently, in 2021, animation use in advertising decreased and expanded by 40% (Buzzflick, 2021).

Animation is undoubtedly growing in importance as a form of advertising: trends and approach. Told, animated advertisements provide us with promotional and amusing videos, so there is no need to ponder why. Customer addicted. This thesis seeks to demonstrate the significance of animated advertising in the modern world. To give a general review of

animated commercials, focusing on realistic animation rendering—and its usefulness in today's advertising world.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

When digital computers first became a part of everyday life in the 1940s, the discipline of computer animation was born (Jim, 2020). In 1960, computer graphics were developed, which paved the way for the invention of two-dimensional (2D) animation. The 1970s. 3-dimensional animation (3D) first appeared in the late 1980s, and The use of 3D animation in film production peaked in the mid-1990s. These advances led to computer animation and visuals (CGA) development. Many academics have talked about how vital animation is to the advertising sector. German professor Patrick Vonderau teaches media and communication studies at Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg, stressed the importance of animation and video games. Computer-generated imagery in marketing and how goods, services, and other things are sold (M. C. Thompson, 2019). He believes that "advertising has influenced modern media; nonetheless, advertising was shaped using animation. According to Ruchi and Deepti Goel Upadhyay, professors of communication studies at the University of Delhi, marketing companies heavily rely on animation in their advertising strategy since it Additionally, motion in commercials makes them more alluring and enticing viewers of all ages, including youngsters, teens, and even adults (Upadhyay, 2017). According to New Jersey native and StudioBinder copywriter Alyssa Maio, the animation is the process of photographing subsequent models or drawings to try to provide the impression of movement in a series (Maio, 2020). She continues by stating that animation represents movement in a succession of images. According to Yasha Vora, a graphic designer at the Souled Store, the animation is a sort of creativity that brings anything to life. She defined animation as Maio, "techniques of recording consecutive drawings or models to generate and appearance of movement and motion" (Vora, 2018). According to her study, advertising is a type of communication intended to persuade potential consumers to buy the commodities, products, and services being marketed. She continues by saying that from the late 19th and early 20th centuries, mass manufacturing and technological breakthroughs have led to an evolution in advertising. Indian professor of fine arts, Deepak Kochhar, describes advertising as a strategy a business or brand uses to market its goods or services to consumers (Kochhar, 2019). Only when viewers recall the commercial can it be said that the ad was successful. The advent of animation into the realm of advertising in the late 19th century had a good and enticing impact on customers' buying intentions as well as their memory of the advertisement's content, according to Sameh Al-Natourm, Robert Krider, and Andrew Gemino, marketing academics (Sameh Al Natourm, 2013). Accordingly, marketing academics Jarmo et al. confirmed in their research that animation boosts attention, which improves the viewer's memory (Jarmo Kuisma, 2010). The artist and advertising specialist Huntley Baldwin from the

United States highlighted the strength of animation in its ability to get away with things that reality cannot achieve, such as creating a world of imagination and enchantment for a product that makes "puffery digestible" (Thompson M. C., 2019). Baldwin explained the four factors that made animation a good choice for ads. It first draws spectators' attention. Second, animation gives goods, services, and products a distinctive brand. Third, animation simplifies complicated concepts into straightforward expressions that everybody can understand. Finally, it can bring an improbable, abstract concept to life.

III. ANIMATION & ADVERTISEMENT

To further underline the significance and applicability of animated ads in today's environment, the next section will continue to show the benefits and drawbacks of animated advertising over live-action commercials. It is essential to remember that there is no such thing as the optimal or optimally optimal strategy for advertising. The decision is highly debatable because the advertisement's purpose and the targeted audience's demographics must be taken into account to establish which kind of advertising is more successful (522 Blog, 2013). However, to determine which alternative is more practical, it is vital to understand the primary benefits and drawbacks of both choices. One thing is sure, regardless of whether you decide to go with real-life or animated advertisements: firms and enterprises need to incorporate videos into their marketing plan, as this is a fruitful approach to boost user engagement and awareness (Hoque, 2020).

➤ *Live Action vs. Animated Advertisements*

There are two broad categories of media content: live-action and animation. Live-action advertisements feature real-life videos of people, animals, objects, and environments. In contrast, animated advertisements entail "using and modifying drawn characters to make them appear moving" (YumYum, 2020). According to Fable Studio, Bristol-based advertising and marketing business, the selection of live-action or animated material is heavily influenced by the intended demographic; yet, animation has frequently been a technique for grabbing the viewer's interest and attention. Chang-Hyun Jin categorizes animation as CGI animation, silhouette animation, cartoon animation, film animation, clay animation, puppet animation, drawn animation, and realistic animation (Jin, 2011). He notes that new technology, such as 3D objects, has made it possible to reproduce animation, remarkably realistic animation. They are increasingly utilized in the television commercial and advertising sector, not only because of their realistic looks but also because of the decreased cost and production time. In addition, while depending on animation to finish their commercial concepts, many businesses want to achieve and produce realistic components. In other words, they are creating the most realistic-looking animation possible. Today, with the progress of computer-generated imagery (CGI), animators are increasingly able to achieve realistic rendering, prompting businesses to reassess the conventional marketing strategy of

using live-action photography. According to Kristin C. Au, senior product designer at Slack, substantial developments in CGI have enabled animation to achieve a new high degree of realism through the use of 3D methods, hence making the animation and plot more relevant and engaging to the viewer (Au, 2014).

Similarly, lecturers from the University of Johannesburg, Fortunate Tatenda Mauyakufa, and Anup Pradhan have emphasized the increased reliance on animation in advertising and movies (Pradhan, 2018). In their essay, they explain that this change is now conceivable since animated (realistic and non-realistic) cartoons may replace performers. Additionally, it has become challenging to identify manufactured landscapes from natural ones. They further emphasize the animation's ability to produce and improve realistic people, sounds, objects, and surroundings. The public is more interested in animated material due to its adaptability and lack of limitations. From the above, it is clear that realistic animation has been enthusiastically received and embraced by the global advertising sector.

➤ *The Benefits of Animation in Advertisements*

Animated ads are cheaper. A production house's cost and Budget would be higher if it filmed a product or service commercial. Because production companies use crews. Teamwork unifies varied ideas, yet it may be costly. The firm must pay the production house for every contracted crew member (light operator, cameraman, DP, retoucher, editor, set, make-up, etc.). Thus, the Company pays for every individual engaged in fulfilling his specialized role and rent equipment for X days or weeks of filming. Animated advertising costs less because it may be created by a smaller team or even a single individual (a "one-man show"). "One man show" refers to an animator who can do everything himself. He may be the DOP, cameraman, videographer, lighting guy, editor, and producer. The animator will use 2D and 3D animation tools to create a commercial. 2 Animation involves a long, well-thought-out process that includes generating a storyboard and much time. Realistic ads employ 3D software. Modeling space and products take patience. Real-life renders require software animation expertise. Using live-action would entail a lengthy process and production staff for the commercial enterprise. Animated advertising may be a "one-man show," reducing expenditures for the Company. Animated ads do not involve locating, recreating, or hiring a set. Nothing is shot in person for animated advertising. Depending on the render's realism, all parts of a live shot are duplicated. You must find or rent a great setting or replicate one in real life. CGI allows the animator to construct the required location, so there is no need to find a place to shoot the commercial. Animation allows the animator and firm to be creative and unrestricted in setting construction. Animation's flexibility and creativity extend beyond places to goods, characters, settings, emotions, and more. From a 3D polygon, the animation becomes lifelike. CGI has improved to the point that it can generate animations that fool the viewer

into thinking a product is real. The 3D model's shadows, lighting, texturing, and camera movement creates a realistic look. Photorealistic computer animation may present unique ideas in strange settings. Animators may construct worlds and environments inaccessible to live-action camera crews. Many firms may use animation for advertising. Animation is more formal and flexible than real-life filming. Animation allows for a clean, soft aesthetic. Abstracts and intricate concepts are harder to demonstrate in real life than digitally. In CGI, where reality does not matter, colors may be manipulated to extremes. This will provide the corporation with an improved version of its product, which will help with advertising by attracting consumers' visual and sensory attention. This is not tricking or manipulating the audience but rather offering the Consumer an idealized depiction of the product, in contrast to real-life filming, which may have defects that post-production cannot eradicate. Live shooting does not ensure a clean, polished look. Advertisements aim to promote a product, object, or service by emphasizing the beauty and eliminating faults. Humans want perfection and want to invest in near perfection. Animated ads may regulate and attain this degree of excellence to increase sales. Lighting is another factor. Natural illumination cannot always make product details apparent, crisp, and exact. The team will be at the mercy of light and time if the shot is outside. Production houses typically employ expensive artificial studio lighting. Due to CGI's independence and improvements, animators may generate excellent lighting without relying on external elements (weather, studio light...). Post-production is a big part of filmmaking and advertising. The live-action video filming has X hours/days, so what is shot cannot be modified. If the corporation wanted to make changes after the final phases, it would not be easy to refilm since it would cost twice. This causes live-action film time and expense unpredictability. Live-action filming has several benefits in any case. A real-life camera may capture actual emotions and human feel. Demonstrating the ad's goal. A genuine camera's narrow depth of focus, light, and reflections assist create the ad's ambient impression. To summarise, find realistic components. Detailed product design, light, natural color palette, and smooth movement. Creating hyperrealistic 3d models using ty flow simulation for 3ds max. Ad animation is fluent, detailed, and animated. The liquid appears and flows realistically. The animated camera, discussed above, enhances the realism of live shooting. Animators produce animated camera motions by moving the camera onscreen and producing keyframes. Animators use tilts, pans, close-ups, and other real-world camera methods to create animations. A corporation considers many factors before making a product video ad. Due to the positives and downsides, animation or live-action video is a top choice for commercial companies.

➤ *The Animation Procedures in Advertising*

A live-action commercial has three stages (Johnston, 2019). Pre-production, production, and post-production are in order. Pre-production is creative. Scripting, graphic design, and hiring comprise this stage. actors/interviewers,

locations/logistics, scheduling/time-management shooting list and crew selection. During manufacture, Live-shooting days, All pre-production decisions will be reenacted for the camera. They are capturing the ad's visuals. After filming, Proceed to post-production. We are finalizing footage processing, editing, editorial work, Motion graphics, sound checks, and voice-overs. Three things Live-action ads have stages. Animated ads have different methods. (2013). First animators must: Project understanding, meaning knowing the Budget, delivery time, brand image, audience, and purpose of the commercial.

Brainstorming follows The concepts, characters/objects, and The tone and script are set. Afterward, Animators produce storyboards. The storyboard depicts a Draft/scratch ad to be evaluated as in the animatic. An animatic is a moving storyboard. Storyboard all recordings (voice-overs, audio, sound effects), pace, and timing of the ad. The asset characters, items, objects, and settings are created by modeling. The commercial is made. Animation follows. All non-movable inventions come to life. The animator will use Camera movement, lighting, shadows, and polish. After when animation is complete, animators render and combine it. Thus, the storyboard went from scratch to animation. Advertisement. The final output is sound. Finishing touches Fix the video's audio and colors once the ad is ready for distribution, in advertising, and after attaining Many adjustments results. A corporation may alter information or color every year. It can if it breaks or the firm wants to change the ultimate product. Live-action reshoots are expensive and difficult to change. Because it has already been done, making a video would be time-consuming. Changing ads' assets is easy. Cartoons, although it is complicated and time-consuming, you can edit your video. Real action (without spending tonnes of money, time, and energy) Therefore, animated ad imagery and digital models are built from scratch, unlike live action, where the product already exists. Thus, animated advertising has no such thing as Live-action ads are limited by what is physically achievable. Possible.

➤ *Critical Thinking (benefit of animated ad)*

It would have been possible to film a live-action advertisement for this product. However, because the customer requested an animated advertisement, there was greater freedom in accomplishing the client's ad concept. The first advantage is boosting the product's visual appeal and vitality while enhancing its functionality and perceived worth. Additionally, it made the product appear more avant-garde and artistic. Moreover, since it is a simple object with a simple mechanism that is readily transportable, it is convenient. Shooting it in real life may have been somewhat tedious. Animation afforded a conceivable dull system a visual boost using captivating visuals and animation bringing life and motion to a static object, which can never be achieved using live shots.

The animation enabled a zoom into a tiny component detail. For example, the manufactured water drop was depicted gliding down a leaf and falling via a hole. The use of animation enabled the client to create the desired atmosphere. The atmosphere they like to associate with their goods. In this instance, the bright, jungle, nature-like setting.

Lastly, animation enabled the customer to make revisions and demands during the project's duration. It was engaging only with the animation agency. Consequently, spending time and reducing the ad crew and group.

➤ *The Effect of Animated ads on the Consumer*

The popularity of animated adverts in today's advertising environment is the best indication that they have a substantial effect and influence on customers. The audience in New York praised the rising immersion of enormous 3D animated billboard commercials for their engaging and realistic images (Weaver, 2022). Figure 1 shows a 3D commercial for an orange Nike sneaker box that bursts open to expose a rotating display of Air Max designs while hinting at the motivation behind each shoe. According to Ethan Jakab, co-founder of "Blunt Action," "these eye-catching 3D billboards are fast becoming highly popular since people are loving the realistic illusion; therefore making them stop and look twice" (Holtz, 2022). The unique campaign elicited a strong response on social media and in person among those traveling through Shinjuku Station, one of the busiest railway stations in the world. Most responses commended the Nike sneaker box's realistic movement toward the audience. They also liked the intriguing image, which made them want to watch the commercial again and again. Some others claimed that the commercial was animated yet appeared genuine, making it even more appealing and enticing.

Fig 1 (3D Commercial For An Orange Nike Sneaker)

Another realistic 3D advertisement that drew viewers' attention was the cat commercial in Japan. In Shinjuku, a three-story-high high-tech billboard unveiled a new realistic 3D ad depicting a gigantic 3D calico cat, as shown in figure 2. The cat gets up around 7 a.m., sleeps in the afternoon, and finally turns off the screen at 1 a.m. (Imada, 2021). MicroAd Digital Signage and Yunika Vision created this advertisement to demonstrate the future possibilities of 3D advertising (Hidrly, 2021). This charming 3D cat, like the other 3D commercial, went viral all over the internet, with viewers providing excellent feedback and comments. According to Takayuki Ohkawa, a representative of one of the businesses that designed this billboard, the primary motivation for developing this ad was the very dark environment that engulfed the city as a result of the pandemic, and this cat was an attempt to reinvigorate and lighten up the city. Their endeavor was well received, and their goal of 30 was met. A pedestrian, Ryoko Kikuchi, reported that when she was walking home from the movies, the enormous cat sitting down licking its paws and meowing was too sweet and made her heart melt. Many individuals felt the same way and communicated on numerous social media sites, including Twitter, Tiktok, YouTube, and Instagram. The majority of responses expressed people's excitement at this rare realistic sight on the streets of Japan. Others stated that they were attracted by the interactive quality of this ad, in which the cat appears to be engaging with the humans. According to Mr. Shimoda, a marketing professional, the impact was more than expected, as many people gathered in front of the billboard to film the cat's various moves and antics (NYT, 2021).

Fig 2 (3D Ad Depicting a Gigantic 3D Calico Cat)

The significant increase in demand, as well as investments in the digital world and animation, is evidence that the dynamics of the world are shifting. There is no denying the fact that digitization and animation have become deeply ingrained in our lives and that this trend will continue to shape the globe in the years to come.

IV. CONCLUSION

An excellent marketing method for enhancing the presentation of a product or service is 3D animation. Modern corporations include animated advertisements in their digital marketing tactics to ensure strong sales for their products and services. Animation is unquestionably more formalistic and adaptable in comparison to the actual shooting. Creating a tidy and gentle appearance requires a great deal of versatility.

In animated form, This is one of many examples illustrating abstract and intricate nature. Creating real-world concepts is more complex than digital ones. Animating will permit enterprises to enhance the appearance of the product or service they want to offer. Despite the visuals, digital models must be created from scratch in animated advertisements. Unlike live-action videos where the product already exists, the client can create the product from scratch. Due to the adaptable nature of animation work, he may easily communicate his needs. So departing Unlike live-action advertisements, which are limited to what is achievable, there is no place for the phrase "impossible." physically attainable.

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